

DIRECTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND PROMOTION OF THE "WOOD'S TOWN AND KOZY" PROJECT

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Abstract

The village of Koshnitsa, located in Dubasari district, was considered as a tourist destination for development and promotion. Reasons for the development of rural tourism include social and economic factors. For the economy, agrotourism plays an important role as an additional source of income and support for farmers who have lost their appeal and consequently their incomes due to increasing urban development. Today, farmers have the opportunity to earn more money. Tourists who reject the idea of spending their holidays in a seaside hotel in favor of active, non-traditional recreation frequently choose rural tourism. Beaches, shopping and noisy parties are not what a holiday looks like for everyone. For many people who are tired of metropolitan life, relaxing in nature, in peace and quiet, breathing fresh air and eating natural products is exactly what they want. The aim of the project is to detach mega-city dwellers from the usual hustle and bustle and immerse them in a relaxed and frugal rural life. The main tasks for the project were: to carry out a macro and micro analysis of the tourist destination environment; to develop a project that gives people the opportunity to spend a few days as villagers; to create the idea of promoting a tourist destination.

Key words: *tourism, destination, promotion project, Kozy Town.*

JEL: *Q01, Z32, M51*

The main revelation was that many citizens had never seen an authentic folk costume, sat with a fishing rod at dawn, milked a cow or walked by goats. The ideal place to implement the project was Koshnitsa. This commune in Dubassari district, Moldova is the administrative center of the commune of Koshnitsa, which also includes the village of Pohrebea.

Firstly, the village of Koshnitsa was chosen for its beautiful views and unspoilt nature, and secondly, due to the fact that the famous Kozy Town [4], which attracts dozens of tourists every day, can be found not far from Koshnitsa. Naturally, the village of Koshnitsa with its rural hotels and the Kozy Town destination will perfectly complement each other by attracting tourists, prolonging their enjoyment and thus further developing the Dubasari district and its villages.

Village life could be interesting for other mega-city dwellers such as couples with children and young adults who prefer a healthy lifestyle and environmental awareness. Foreigners who want to get acquainted with cultural traditions and folklore represent another fairly large segment of tourists. To such guests, the natural environment, the national colors and the authenticity of rural life can sometimes be more important than the presence of a TV set in the room. As foreigners choose their leisure destinations mainly through the internet, it is necessary to develop a multilingual website with vivid photos, service descriptions and a price list, as well as regularly post advertisements on foreign travel forums and social networks. As leisure will be offered:

- professional photoshoot with pets dressed in national costumes;
- the opportunity to take care of pets, which will be very interesting for children (milking a cow, feeding the course, collecting eggs, combing a horse);
- master class on homemade cheese and cottage cheese production;
- fishing at dawn.

Figure 1 shows a beautiful view of the Koshnitsa village, site of the planned tourist destination development and promotion project.

Figure 1. Koshnitsa village

Source: edited by authors

A scenic view is not enough to make the decision whether to develop the project idea. In order to have a more comfortable understanding of the different types of factors and risks, a PEST analysis is required. PEST analyses help to identify the political, economic, socio-cultural and technological factors that affect a particular business [2, p. 28]. The results from the analysis can be used to understand the overall picture of the business environment, to make a more detailed planning, to look for new opportunities, to minimize risks. The analysis results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. PEST analysis of the tourist destination "Wood's town and Kozy"

Factors	Potential changes in the tourism industry	Impact on the destination	Possible solutions
Political - changes to the tourism legislation; - tightening of entry rules (visa regimes); - environmental legislation.	- tightening of restrictions; - reduction of visitor numbers; - compliance with certain rules to preserve the environment of destinations.	- termination of revenue depending on destination; - restricting the number of visitors; - introduction of a system of fines in the territory of the destination for breaking the law.	1) Online tours; 2) Development of the local rural areas as destinations; 3) Advertising the destination on social media and maintaining a Tik-Tok account;
Economic - crises in the local and global economy; - rising prices for	- people will spend less on entertainment and leisure and more on essentials;	- tourist destination revenues will decrease; recreational areas will be vacant;	1) Lower prices, promotions aimed at increasing demand; 2) Discount scheme on

services; - improving living standards; - inflation and interest rates.	- people will be less likely to visit the destination; - increase in bank lending rates, making it unprofitable to borrow in the future.	- possible decrease in revenue and visitors; - slowdown in innovation.	certain days, possibility to win a free ticket in competitions; 3) Taking micro-credits below 0%; 4) Attracting foreign sponsors.
Socio-demographic - mass population migration; - changes in population values; - changes in lifestyle, consumption habits, characteristics of tourist behavior; - attitudes towards natural and organic products.	- as Covid restrictions are tightened, for example, people will travel less, habits will change and such behavior will become the norm; - influence on tourists' lifestyles; - the desire to get closer to healthy eating.	- people will choose substitute travel services; - people will be more selective in their choice of places to visit; - visitors who lead a healthy lifestyle will be drawn.	1) Development of new ideas to promote familiar products; creation of hybrid tourism products; 2) Trying to interest the customer with unusual advertising; 3) Developing a variety of environmentally friendly products.
Technology - the introduction of new and various software; - development of transport improvements; - the emergence of new technologies and techniques which are largely used by major travel companies; - access to the latest technologies.	- new technologies and the development of new directions in tourism; - more comfortable conditions for long-term travel.	- loss of customers who are used to traditional tourism; - people will find it easier to spend time on the road in comfort; - attracting customers interested in new technologies.	1) The implementation of technological innovations should take place gradually, while maintaining the regular tourism products; 2) Providing vehicles with air conditioners and places for charging devices; 3) Implementation of QR code system and pocket guides.
The cultural factor - improving the morality and cultural development of the population; - the desire for new impressions.	- the desire to be closer to nature; - people will seek out new places to visit everywhere.	- the emergence of new morally exalted people; - people will visit the destination for new experiences.	1) Development of "drink wine, reconnect with nature, pet goats, listen to the classics" service; 2) Enhancement of the goat service; 3) Running various contests and promotions.

Source: edited by authors

Based on the analysis carried out, the authors can conclude that destination development and quality are primarily influenced by seasonal factors, given that the destination will be more relevant in warm seasons, as well as by the possible level of inflation.

Discount schemes and visitor loyalty programmers can be seen as the most promising solutions. The creation of hybrid tourism products will also be of interest for an unusual approach. In order to investigate aspects of the internal environment and the influence of external factors, the authors chose the SWOT analysis method [1, p. 18]. A SWOT analysis is a way to analyze various aspects of a company and determine how competitive it is. It can help to decide what strategies should be used in the future to achieve further success. The results of the analysis are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. SWOT analysis of the tourist destination "Wood's town and Kozy"

SWOT – analysis	Strengths	Weaknesses
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the only goat town in the Republic of Moldova; - high-quality advertising; - high level of service. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - inconvenient location; - high prices; - small area at the moment.
Possibilities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - use social networks for promotion; - development of new recreational activities for tourists; - attracting foreign tourists. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - setting up a website in a foreign language; - development of animation activities within the tourist complex; - construction of new infrastructure facilities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - expanding territories; - familiarizing the population with the Koshnitsa village through guided tours; - attracting tourists to agricultural activities.
Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - reduction of revenue from some customers; - significant cost increases related to the introduction of innovations; - tourist visits to destinations will be rare or one-off. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - increase in prices for tourist services; - attracting sponsors, influential people in Moldova and abroad; - developing loyalty programmes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - creation of bonuses; - development of a discount system and advantageous offers for tourists.

Source: edited by authors

The most important criterion for increasing market share and strengthening a company's leading position in the industry is competitiveness. It represents a company's ability to compete with other players in the market, to attract and retain consumers with fewer resources [5, p. 20]. The competitiveness project indicates whether it meets the specific needs of consumers compared to the best similar projects, is able to outperform others, uses its advantages in achieving its goals, its suggestion is competitive [3, p. 26].

The authors conducted an analysis of the project's competitiveness. The Kozy destination has been compared with a destination currently under development. The results of the study are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Competitiveness analysis of "Wood's town and Kozy" destination

Competitiveness analysis	Tourist destination "Wood's town"		Tourist destination "Kozy"	
	Current situation	Desired situation	Current situation	Desired situation
Territorial product <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - specific characteristics of the territory; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - tourist destination with beautiful views, has 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - a popular destination for retreat in nature and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - is located in a scenic area with a charming panoramic view; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - is located in a beautiful place; - high rating.

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- an individual's assessment of the place; - management system, management.	many development directions - tourist destination is not particularly developed	hotels; - the destination is a success.	- average rating.	
Territorial product price - what costs will be incurred by someone staying within the territory; - price level (high, medium, low).	- costs for: transport, possible additions (photographer, products); -average.	- costs for: transport, possible additions (photographer, products).	costs of: transport, guides, meals; -low.	costs of: transport, guides, meals; -low.
Location of the territorial product - evaluation of the location's profitability; - static characteristics of the location; - dynamic characteristics of the location.	- the location is convenient, being located 30 km from Chisinau.		- the location is convenient, being located 30 km from Chisinau.	
Promotion of the territorial product - how is information communicated to tourists? - what measures are taken to stimulate demand?	- social networking, recommendations.	- social networks, websites, leaflets, banners, blogger advertising.	- social networking, recommendations.	- advertising, cooperation with brands.
The tourism service supply process - description of the types and level of services in the tourist destination; - additional services that improve the tourism service supply process.	- professional photoshoot with pets dressed in national costumes; - the opportunity to take care of pets, which will be very interesting for children (milking a cow, feeding the course, collecting eggs, combing a horse); - master class on homemade cheese and cottage cheese production; - fishing at dawn; - accommodation and meals.		- accommodation, meals, transfer, guide, boat ride, gazebo.	- accommodation, meals, transfer, guide, gazebo, horse riding, surfing.
People, staff - locals (characteristics);	- friendly, keen to provide	- service professionals:	- receptive, sophisticated, elegant, reserved, friendly, as well as activists.	

- opportunity to participate in tourist activities in the area.	quality service.	farmers, cooks, waiters, maids.	
Physical environment - the environment surrounding the tourist during his stay in the destination.	- rustic view, nature, fields, pond.		- hills, beautiful view of the villages, fresh air.

Source: edited by authors

The "Wood town and Kozy" project developed by the authors can primarily help the location to gain recognition among local and foreign tourists, as well as to support the development of Moldovan tourism to a new international level. The authors have compiled a description of the tourist destination, analyzed the micro and macro environments, and have also developed a promotion project for the tourist destination, thus fulfilling all the tasks of the project.

Conclusion

Following the analysis carried out, the "Wood's town and Kozy" project identify the possibilities of implementing a project to promote a tourist destination, it may be concluded that, once an appropriate development plan is drawn up, as a tourist destination, "Wood's town and Kozy" has adequate potential to compete on an equal footing with competitors developing in the same area. Therefore, we can draw the following conclusions: the tourist infrastructure of our destination is underdeveloped; the destination may not be of interest to rural residents; the destination is seasonal and depends on weather conditions.

Recommendations may include the following: with sufficient sponsorship and involvement of local residents, the tourist destination can attract short-term, periodic as well as long-term interest; seasonal and long-term interest should be maintained, as this contributes to the development and improvement of local tourist services; the Kozy Town and Wood's Town projects could perfectly complement each other.

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